

POLICY																						
	Agricultural Sciences	Arts & Humanities	Biology & Biochemistry	Chemistry	Clinical Medicine	Computer Science	Economics & Business	Engineering	Environment/Ecology	Geosciences	Immunology	Materials Science	Mathematics	Microbiology	Molecular Biology & Genetics	Neuroscience & Behavior	Pharmacology & Toxicology	Physics	Plant & Animal Science	Psychiatry/Psychology	Social Sciences, General	Space Sciences
Pompeu Fabra University UPF	1	0	10	0	24	0	28	0	29	0	0	0	0	8	3	5	0	4	11	9		
U Autónoma de Madrid UAM	4	0	0	0	65	0	4	0	37	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	21	0	0	
U Complutense de Madrid UCM	6	1	0	1	30	11	3	2	36	12	2	0	0	4	0	5	7	0	4	12	13	0
U de Alcalá UAH				0	6	0		4	13	6		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
U de Barcelona UB	13	1	3	0	254	0	15	8	16	23	221	1	0	67	2	21	14	9	14	73	11	0
U de Cádiz UCA		1		0		4			21								0		0	1	0	
U de Cantabria UNICAN		0			10	0	0		50	23		0		1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
U de Castilla-La Mancha UCLM	0		0	3	26		2	2		0		4	0			0	0				0	
U de Córdoba UCO	0	0	1	0	8	0	0	0			4	0	0	3	0		0		0	19	16	
U de Granada UGR	13	0	3	2	27	21	0	1	6	2	0	0	0	0		3	3	0	0	4	16	0
U de La Laguna ULL			0	0		1			0	0			0						0		3	0
U de Las Palmas de Gran Canaria ULPGC	14	0	1		7	0	1			0				0	1				0	1	0	
U de Málaga UMA	8		0	0	9	2			131	0		0			4	0			38	4	6	
U de Murcia UM	0		0	2	22	0		0		14	2			0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	
U de Navarra UNAV	102		0		48		3	0			0			0	7	0	0		0	0	3	
U de Oviedo UNIOVI	0	0	1	0	5	0	1	0	6					0	0	1	0	4	26	4	0	
U de Santiago de Compostela USC	0		0	0	0	0		6	3	0		0	0	0	0	8	0	2	0	7	0	
U de Sevilla US	1	0	0	0	2	0	0		0	0	25		19		2	2	0	0	0	0	1	
U de Valencia UV	16	0	0	0	67	0	2	1	13	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	10	10	2	
U de Zaragoza UNIZAR	29	0	0	0	8	1	3	3		3		0	0	0	0	0	0	2	8	0		
U del País Vasco EHU	4	1	0	0	1	0		7	16	1		0	0			1	1	0	0	4	1	0
U Europea de Madrid CEU			0		6									0	0	0				0		
U Miguel Hernández UMH	0		0		4	0			0		7		0	0	0	0				0	0	
U Rey Juan Carlos URJC	0		0		3	1		0	8	0		0		1				2	0	0	1	
U Rovira i Virgili URV	21	1	0	0	22	1		1	3	5		0	0			2	0	0	0	0	2	
U de Vigo UVIGO	2			1	0	0		19	33	19		0	0			0	0	0			0	
U Autónoma de Barcelona UAB	1	0	0	0	56	1	12	0	83	7	34	0	0	9	0	55	5	0	3	10	77	
U Politècnica de València UPV	0		0	0	0	1	6	2			4	0		0			0	6			1	